

GEOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GABBROIC INTRUSIVE BODIES IN THE SHA-KALERI YOUNGER GRANITE COMPLEX, CENTRAL NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Large discrete gabbroic intrusive bodies outcrop within the Tof sub-unit of the Sha-Kaleri Jurassic Younger Granite Complex, situated at the southwestern end of the Jos Plateau. They were sampled and analysed for their major and trace element compositions with a view to determining their geochemical characteristics and tectonic setting. The gabbroic rocks co-exist with hybrid rocks of composition in-between the gabbros and the granite porphyry and the extrusive equivalent basaltic rocks. The rocks are composed essentially of plagioclase and hornblende with minor pyroxene (titaniferous augite) and olivine similar to the composition of the co-existing basalts of presumably Cenozoic age. The gabbros display enrichment in incompatible elements (Rb, Th, U, K, Nb, and Sr) compared to the Mid Ocean Ridge Basalt (MORB). The relatively wide variation in CaO/TiO₂ ratios (3.35 – 7.95) of these gabbros is in good agreement with their formation by fractional crystallization process. This is further attested to by their wide variations in incompatible element ratios (Rb/Sr= 0.03-0.32); Zr/Nb=1.03-8.48); Th/U=0.97-1.25) and U/Pb=0.19-0.47). They also present trace element compositions similar to that of the Ocean Floor Basalt (OFB) and Jos Plateau Basalts suggesting that they must have been derived from the same parent mantellic magma.

KEYWORDS : Gabbro, Younger Granites, Basalts, mid-oceanic ridge basalts, Incompatible elements, ocean ridge basalts.

INTRODUCTION

Gabbroic rocks outcrop in a few Jurassic Younger Granite ring complexes in Nigeria (Macleod *et al.*, 1971). They make up a minor part (about 1%) of the complex in which they occur. Occurrences of these gabbroic intrusions have been reported at Kofayi ring complex, northeast of Jos Plateau, at Sara-fier complex, southeast of Jos Plateau and at Sha-Kaleri complex southwest of the Jos Plateau to mention but a few. The Mama gabbros, which form the subject of this investigation, outcrop within the Sha-Kaleri complex where the largest volume of mafic intrusive bodies has been observed. They occur as intrusive or as veined sill-like bodies within the host granitic rocks. Hybrid rocks of compositions in-between these two rock types do occur. It is however neither clear if the gabbros predate other granitic rock units nor it is clear as to their origin vis-à-vis the overlying volcanic equivalent rocks, the Cenozoic basalts. Thus, it is difficult to fix these gabbros in their rightful place as it relates to the evolution of the Jurassic Younger Granite complexes. This paper therefore attempts to determine the geochemical characteristics and the origin of these gabbros in comparison with their volcanic equivalent basaltic rocks in the Sha-Kaleri Younger granite complex.

Geology and Petrography

Sha-Kaleri Younger Granite complex is situated southwest of the Jos Plateau and marks the southern boundary of the Plateau with the low-lying Paleozoic-Precambrian Basement into which the granites intruded. The complex is the third largest of all the Younger Granite complexes in Nigeria and occupies a superficial area of nearly 400 km². It is sub-divided into three distinct minor complexes, which include from north to the south the Kaleri, Monguna and Tof sub-complexes (Figure 1)

The Mama gabbros outcrop within the Tof sub-complex (Figure 1) as several phases of intrusive bodies within the granite porphyry. At the contact between these gabbros and granite porphyry, the gabbros are net-veined by the porphyry parallel to the contact. Hybrid rocks probably formed by the assimilation of the gabbroic xenolith in the granite porphyry magma co-exist.

They have poikilitic to subophitic texture but they present similar mineralogical compositions. The only variation is in the proportion of hornblende and plagioclase the principal visible constituent minerals. Other minerals such as titaniferous augite occur as accessories together with biotite, olivine and iron oxide in the hornblende.

ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES

Nine rock samples were crushed and milled to less than 125µm powder for geochemical analysis. Only the following major elements (K₂O, MnO, Fe₂O₃, CaO, TiO₂) and trace elements (V, Cr, Ni, Co, Cu, Zn, As, Pb, Br, Rb, Sr, Y, Zr, Nb, Mo, Th, U) were analyzed. Other major elements especially SiO₂ were not analyzed for lack of facility. The analysis was carried out using the Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence (ED-XRF) technique at the Centre for Energy, Research and Training (CERT), Zaria. For both major and trace element analyses, the rock powder was pressed into pellets. The instrument was calibrated using recommended international standards at each time necessary. The precision and accuracy of the data were lower than 1% for major elements and 0.05% for trace elements.

Geochemical Results

The major and trace element compositions of the gabbros from the study area are presented in Table 1.

Major elements

In general, the rocks present relatively lower concentrations in CaO, Fe₂O₃, K₂O and higher TiO₂ compared to their equivalent volcanic basaltic rocks of the Jos Plateau. For all the rocks put together, the percentages of K₂O vary narrowly (0.72-0.99Wt%) as oppose to the relatively wide variations in the other major elements analysed (for example, TiO₂=0.76-2.30Wt%; CaO=5.72 – 7.61Wt%; Fe₂O₃=6.01-7.55 Wt%). On the variation plots of TiO₂ Wt%, MnO Wt% and CaO Wt% versus Fe₂O₃ Wt% (Figures 2-4), the rocks define positive correlations. Contrarily in K₂O Wt% and Fe₂O₃ Wt% variation diagram (Figure 5), the proportions of K₂O Wt % do not seem vary significantly with the increase in that of Fe₂O₃Wt%. There is however a wide range of variation in their CaO/TiO₂ ratios (3.35-7.95).

Trace elements

The trace element data were displayed in MORB normalized spidergraphs and tectonic discrimination diagrams of Pearce and Cann, (1973); Winchester and Floyd, (1977); Meschede, (1986) and Pearce, (1975).

In the MORB-normalized spidergraphs, all the rocks display consistent variations in the trace elements, thus exhibiting similar distribution patterns. Generally, the rocks are enriched in incompatible elements (K, Rb, Th, U, Nb, Sr and are slightly depleted in High field Strength elements (Zr, Ti and Y) relative to the Mid Oceanic Ridge Basalts (MORB). Of note are the significant positive anomalies in Th (100-150 x MORB) and U (200-400 x MORB). In contrast however, samples SG4 and 9 are relatively depleted in Sr as oppose to Y enrichment in sample SG2 relative to MORB (Figures 6-7).

The gabbros when plotted in the discrimination diagram of Winchester and Floyd, (1977) (Figure 8) fall within the domain of sub-alkaline to alkaline fields. They plot in the PMORB field in the tectonic discrimination diagram of Meschede, (1986) (Figure 9). This is further attested to by exhibiting similar characteristics as Ocean Floor Basalts (OFB) in the log Ti (ppm) versus log Cr (ppm) of Pearce, (1975) (Figure 10) and in the Ti (ppm) versus Zr (ppm) diagram of Pearce and Cann, (1973) (Figure 11).

DISCUSSION

The variations in the content of CaO, TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ will here be used since they control the crystallization of pyroxene and plagioclase, which are the principal constituent minerals in these gabbros. The systematic progressive increases in the Fe₂O₃ either with CaO or TiO₂ and the relatively wide variations of CaO/TiO₂ ratios (3.35 – 7.95) for all the rocks suggest their formation by fractional crystallization process from the same magma source. Their relatively significant ranges in the variations of incompatible element ratios (e.g. Rb/Sr=0.03 – 0.32; Zr/Nb=1.03 – 8.48; Th/U=0.97 – 1.25; and U/Pb=0.19 – 0.47) further support this assertion.

By their characteristic enrichment in incompatible elements relative to compatible elements they are comparable to the co-existing extrusive equivalent basaltic rocks of the Jos Plateau (Lar and Tsalha, 2005). They however differ from the Jos Plateau basalts by their relatively lower percentages in Fe₂O₃ and CaO, and higher tenors in TiO₂. This is understandable only if these gabbros are the products of the differentiation of the same magma from which these basalts were also derived ab-initio. Compared to the Mid Oceanic Ridge Basalts (MORB),

they differ by their relative enrichment in the incompatible elements (K, Rb, Th, U, Nb, Sr). The composition of the gabbros in Zr, Nb, Y and TiO₂ is indicative of their alkaline nature (Winchester and Floyd, 1977), which is further attested to by their strong positive anomalies in Nb, Th and U. While most of these gabbros display Zr/Nb ratios between 1.07 and 5.48 suggesting their derivation from sources akin to those of the Ocean Floor alkaline Basalts (OFB), few of them display relatively higher ratios (6.89 – 8.48) also suggesting an origin similar to that of the enriched mantle Oceanic Island Basalts (EM OIB). However, these higher Zr/Nb ratios can be explained either by fractionation of these elements or by the interaction of the slow cooling gabbroic magma within the continent.

CONCLUSION

From the data presented and the discussions that followed, the following conclusions can be reached; The gabbros display geochemical characteristics identical to that of the extrusive alkaline basalts of Jos Plateau suggesting a derivation from the similar parent magma. They however differ by their relatively lower concentrations in Fe₂O₃ and CaO, and higher concentrations in TiO₂.

They represent essentially the product of the fractional crystallization of the same parent mantle magma from where the Basalts of the Jos Plateau were derived.

Compared to Mid Oceanic Ridge Basalts (MORB), the gabbros display relative enrichment in incompatible elements (K, Rb, Th, U, Nb, Sr).

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Fig 2: TiO₂ wt % Versus Fe₂O₃ wt% variation plot of the Mama gabbros.

Fig 3: MnO wt % Versus Fe₂O₃ wt% variation plot of the Mama gabbros.

Fig 4 CaO wt % Versus Fe₂O₃ wt% variation plot of the Mama gabbros.

Fig 5: K₂O wt % Versus Fe₂O₃ wt% variation plot for rocks of the study area.

Fig 6: MORB- normalized spiderdiagram for samples SG1-SG6.

Fig 7: MORB- normalized spiderdiagram for samples SG7-SG9.

Fig 8: Log(Zr/TiO₂) Versus Log(Nb/Y) classification diagram (After Floyd, 1977).

Fig 9: Nb*2 - Zr/4 - tectonic discrimination diagram (After Meschede, 1986).

Fig 10: Log Ti(ppm) Versus Log Cr(ppm) tectonic discrimination for rocks of the study area (After Pearce, 1975).

Fig 11: Ti(ppm) Versus Cr(ppm) tectonic discrimination for rocks of the study area (After Pearce and Cann, 1973).

Table 1:Major (wt.%) and Trace element (ppm) compositions of Mama Gabbros.

	Major Elements(wt.%)					Trace Elements (ppm)																	Element Ratios				
	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	MnO	Fe ₂ O ₃	V	Cr	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Pb	Br	Rb	Sr	Y	Zr	Nb	Mo	Th	U	CaO/TiO ₂	Zr/Nb	Th/U	U/Pb	Rb/Sr
SG- 1	0.84	6.04	0.76	0.15	6.01	910	589	258	200	120	772	56.3	82	18	31	180	12	60	13.3	7.30	26	22.4	7.95	4.51	1.2	0.27	0.17
SG -2	0.99	4.72	1.48	0.10	7.55	802	563	439	145	108	13.6	49.1	70.7	23.1	26	299	40	30	28	9.27	23	18.4	3.19	1.07	1.3	0.26	0.09
SG -3	0.91	6.30	1.10	0.12	7.21	881	572	370	190	120	73	62.3	88.4	20.1	15	230	13	59	7.00	7.20	21	17	5.73	8.43	1.2	0.19	0.07
SG -4	0.72	7.73	2.31	0.08	5.10	987	565	238	201	105	64.7	44.7	63.9	16.2	13	57	13	38	6.96	6.85	26	26.6	3.35	5.46	1	0.42	0.23
SG – 5	0.91	6.29	1.05	0.21	7.21	881	572	368	190	119	72.8	62.3	88.4	20.1	15	228	13	59	6.96	8.27	21	16.9	5.99	8.48	1.2	0.19	0.07
SG -6	0.99	5.72	1.28	0.10	7.00	802	563	542	246	103	186	49.1	70.7	23.1	26	300	30	60	58	8.27	23	30.2	4.47	1.03	0.8	0.43	0.09
SG -7	0.83	7.51	2.00	0.08	6.08	987	565	238	201	225	64.7	44.7	63.9	16.2	13	57	13	48	6.96	7.85	27	26.6	3.76	6.89	1	0.42	0.23
SG -8	0.98	7.61	1.19	0.08	7.25	945	684	480	144	115	122	49	71.7	30	54	167	19	41	13.5	6.42	22	17.3	6.39	3.04	1.3	0.24	0.32
SG -9	0.84	6.04	0.76	0.15	6.01	945	684	480	144	115	122	49	69.1	16.4	54	167	19	41	13.5	6.40	22	17.3	7.95	3.04	1.3	0.25	0.32